

TO CREATE CONDITION FOR LANGUAGE LEARNERS

Ummatov Bakhtiyor

Teacher of the department "English language and literature" of the Faculty of Philology
Gulistan State University

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Below we consider the necessary conditions for foreign language learners:

1) **Immersion.** When teaching literacy children should be saturated with language. This includes meaningful reading and writing and lots of talk time. A book before bed instead of television, your child's name on the refrigerator spelled out in block letters, nursery rhymes and poems recited out loud. We want to create a culture of literacy at home.

2) **Demonstration.** When a child is learning language they receive thousands of demonstrations of speech all the time, every day. Demonstration in this sense refers to demonstrating to a child not just how you read and write but how you LEARN to read and write. This involves pointing at words as you say them, doing shared writing exercises, and, at home, demonstrating your own desire to read. I have spoken [before](#) about the importance of a strong "book" presence in the home. Children model what you do, not what you say. Read.

3) **Approximation.** Young children use approximation in speech as they are learning to talk. They often do the same as they are learning to write. While a child is praised when they say "writed" they might be reprimanded when they put the same thing down on paper. Children should be encouraged to use approximations both in oral and written language. They are testing out the literary waters and beginning to store information that they will refine as time goes on.

4) **Employment or Use.** There should be plenty of opportunities to engage in reading and writing. There should be independent reading and writing time as well as shared reading and writing time. Remember our key word: abundance.

5) **Responsibility.** This is a condition I really believe in and love. It refers to the idea that children should be able to decide what topic and what conventions of language they want to master based on their individual needs. They should be responsible for the direction of their own language learning. If a child lives in Southern California, he or she might want to read and write about the ocean. If a child loves art, he or she might want to learn how to write the colors. When children are engaged in what they are learning they retain information much better and often at a much faster rate. Not to mention that then they begin to develop not just a need *for* but a love *of* reading and writing.

6) **Feedback or Response.** The example Cambourne uses is this one: "How do we get a child to progress from saying 'I goed downtown' to 'I went downtown?'" Correcting a child, no matter how tempting, is not the answer. Instead we should use what is called "feedback and response." When a child says to you "I goed downtown" instead of saying "it's *went* downtown," we repeat their statement using the correct form of speech and then expand on it.

Example: "You went downtown? How exciting! What did you do when you went downtown?" When a child hears the correct form in a non-corrective way it registers in their memory. By expanding the statement we also get the child to continue actively constructing language. The same method should be employed in a reading a writing workshop. Approximations should be encouraged and congratulated and then built on verbally. If a child has written "I goed downtown" on the page we can say the same thing in response that we would to a verbal comment and then encourage the child to keep writing from there.

7) **Expectation.** Teachers (and parents) can expect that when all seven of these conditions have been met that children *will* learn how to read and write. Expectation is important when it comes to literacy. We want to let children grow with words in their own time while simultaneously retaining the belief that they will learn, and flourish.

REFERENCES

1. Swain, Merrill., and Lapkin, Sharon. (1995). Problems in Output and The Cognitive Processes They Generate: A Step Towards Second Language Learning. *Applied Linguistics*, 16, 370-391.
2. Lewis, Gwyn., Jones, Bryn., and Baker, Colin. (2012b). Translanguaging: Developing Its Conceptualisation and Contextualisation. *Educational Research and Evaluation: An International Journal on Theory and Practice*, 18(7), 655-670.
3. Ellis, Rod. (2001). Investigating Form-Focused Instruction. *Language Learning*, 51(1), 1-46.
4. Creese, Angela., and Blackledge, Adrian. (2010). Translanguaging in the Bilingual Classroom: A Pedagogy for Learning and Teaching? *Modern Language Journal*, 94, (103-115).
5. Baker, Colin. (2011). *Foundations of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism* (5th ed.). Clevedon, UK: Multilingual Matters.